

ATTITUDE OF PUPIL TEACHERS TOWARDS TEACHING PROFESSION

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Abstract

Teaching has been regarded as a dynamic activity that requires a positive attitude and competitive nature from the teachers. The Modern scenario of the teaching profession demands from its practitioners to be the facilitator of learning. To make the teaching-learning process successful or to increase its effectiveness, teachers must have a favorable attitude towards the teaching profession because the teacher is the most important person in the entire education process. The present study aims to investigate the attitude of pupil teachers toward the teaching profession. 124 pupil teachers in all the three campuses of H.N.B.G.U. (a central university) participated as the total sample in the study. A standardized tool by Dr. Umme Kulsum was used to measure the pupil-teacher's attitude toward the teaching profession. The tool consists of 55 statements related to academic, administrative, co-curricular, socio-psychological, and economic aspects of the teaching profession. The tool was circulated to collect the data. A survey method was adopted to collect the data. The data then were analyzed with Excel software. The result showed that the pupil teachers have a moderate level of attitude towards the teaching profession. Gender, locality, and stream wise there is no significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards the teaching profession. The result of the study indicates that Self-finance pupil teachers have comparatively more favorable attitude than the Government pupil teachers towards teaching profession.

Keywords: Teaching Attitude, Pupil teachers, teaching profession.

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Introduction

Education is one of the most responsible factors for the development of any nation and society. Imparting quality education depends on the competence and characteristics of a good teacher. To be a good teacher a teacher must be equipped with some essential professional qualities. Teaching has been regarded as the noblest profession. In 1952-53 the secondary education commission report strongly argued in favor of a teacher that, a teacher has to play a vital role in the educational reconstruction and in doing so the personal qualities, educational qualification, professional competency, and the place he occupies in the society are the important factors. (Parvez 2010) said that the best teachers can draw great outcomes from the worst systems.

Teaching is a process in which teachers and students come into contact with each other and work toward specific objectives. The entire process depends on the interaction between the teacher and the students. Teaching helps to improve and enhance the learning process. The quality of teaching ensures and determines the quality of learning.

Teaching has been regarded as an art as well as a science. Dedication to the subject and a healthy relationship with the learners is responsible for the quality of teaching. Teaching is always about two-way communication between the teacher and the learner about exchanging good experiences and knowledge (Chawla & Mittal 2013). Being a lifelong process in Education the role of the teacher is always there. The absence of quality teachers makes the education process ineffective and incomplete. It is a teacher who acts as a medium in the effective teaching-learning process (Sarkar & Behera 2016). In the process of education, teaching plays a vital role in the development of human resources. The quality of teaching and education affects and enhances the standards of a country. The educated young generation can serve effectively to transfer education to the next generations (Zaidi 2015). Teaching has an important role to play in the life of the citizens of a society. It is the teaching profession in which there is a large scope for social work and welfare than any other profession (Nenty et al., 2015). Teaching has a wide role to play in affecting skills and promoting behavior. It is the attitude of teachers which plays a vital role in making the teaching profession competent (Sarkar & Behera 2016).

It has been always a matter of debate, whether teaching is a mission or a profession. In recent times teaching has been accepted as a profession. But being so, it has been regarded as the noblest profession of all. It is only through this profession that the teacher does not only affect

the pupils but the teacher can impact many generations. Though, this impact may be positive or negative. In this sense, the importance of the teaching profession increases.

The success of the teaching profession depends on the attitude of the people involved in it. A positive and sound attitude towards the teaching profession works as a vital factor in ensuring the success of teaching and learning. The teaching profession allows the future to be a good citizen. It also allows the teacher to do something for the development of the society. The teaching profession has the scope to enhance knowledge. It is the attitude of teachers toward the teaching profession which sets the pride and commitment of teachers towards the profession (Maheshwari 2019).

Attitude is the psychological construct of a person as to how he feels or thinks about some object, event, thing, etc. It is a positive or negative tendency or predisposition about something or someone. In general, the way a person views and evaluates his surrounding constitutes his attitude. Attitude as a psychological construct can be observed as a complete behavior constitutes by cognitive, affective, and psychomotor behavior. A person can be positive and negative in their attitude toward an object or event at the same time (Ozdemir & Demircioğlu 2016).

Mohammad Parvez1 & Mohd Shakir (2013) in their study investigated the attitude of prospective teachers towards the teaching profession. The finding of the study showed a significant difference between the attitude of private and public B.Ed. institution's prospective teachers. The study showed that there is no significant difference among the B.Ed. students concerning the category of male and female, science and social science, Muslim and non-Muslim.

Objective of the study

1. To assess the level of attitude of pupil teachers towards the teaching profession.
2. To study gender, stream, locality-wise, and type of institute, and the attitude of pupil teachers towards the teaching profession.

Hypotheses of the study

H01: There is no significant difference between the attitude of male and female pupil teachers towards the teaching profession.

H02: There is no significant difference between the attitude of Arts and Science stream pupil teachers towards the teaching profession.

H03: There is no significant difference between the attitude of pupil teachers towards the teaching profession, living in urban and rural areas.

H04: There is no significant difference between the attitudes of Government and Self-finance pupil teachers toward the teaching profession.

Research Method

The descriptive survey method was used in the present study. All the pupil teachers in three campuses of H.N.B.G.U. the central university were selected as the total population by the purposive sampling technique. 124 pupil teachers of a total of 197 in all three campuses of the HNB Garhwal University participated in the study by filling out the questionnaire. A standardized tool was used to collect the required data. The tool "Attitude scale towards teaching profession" was developed and standardized by Dr. Umme Kulsum. The items of the questionnaire cover the five areas of the teaching profession academic, administrative, co-curricular, socio-psychological, and economic. The tool consisted of 55 statements on the teaching profession, out of which 25 items were having a positive attitude towards the teaching profession and 30 items were having a negative attitude towards the teaching profession. The tool is developed with a four-point rating scale with strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree respectively.

Procedure for Data Analysis: A standardized tool was applied for collecting the data. All three campuses of H.N.B.G.U. a central university were selected as the population. The tool was administered among all the pupil teachers of all the three campuses. All the three campuses in the university participated in filling out the required questionnaire. MS Excel software was used for analyzing the gathered data. The percentage analysis and t-test were applied for the analysis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:-

1- Demographic characteristics of the pupil teachers.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics.

Gender	N (%)	Stream	N (%)	Locality	N (%)	Institute	N (%)
Male	61(49%)	Arts	60(48%)	Urban	40(32%)	Government	75(60%)
Female	63(51%)	Science	64(52%)	Rural	84(68%)	Self-finance	49(40%)
Total	124(100%)	Total	124(100%)	Total	124(100%)	Total	124(100%)

Table 1: shows the demographic characteristics of pupil teachers who participated in the study, out of 124; there were 61 male and 63 female pupil teachers with a percentage of 49 and 51

respectively. Of the total 124 pupil teachers there were 60 arts stream pupil teachers and 64 science stream pupil teachers with a percentage of 48 & 52 respectively and there were 40 urban and 84 rural pupil teachers with a percentage of 32 and 68 respectively. Out of 124, 75 were government and 49 were self-financed pupil teachers, the percentage of which was 60 and 40 respectively.

2-Analysis of the attitude of pupil teachers towards the teaching Profession based on the cut-off point.

Table 2: Mean and Std. a score of the pupil teacher's attitude towards the teaching profession

Variable	Frequency(N)	Mean	S.D
Teaching Profession	124	171.53	12.98

Table 2: shows that the cut-off point here is $M \pm 1\sigma$. It can be seen that the Mean and SD of the attitude towards teaching profession scores on the total sample were 171.53 and 12.98. This means, 184.51 is $M + 1\sigma$. Moreover, 158.55 is $M - 1\sigma$.

3. Percentage analysis of pupil teacher's attitude towards the teaching profession.

Table 3:- Level of an attitude of pupil teachers towards the teaching profession (percentage analysis).

Score	Frequency(N)	Percentage	Level of attitude
Below -158.55	22	18%	Low altitude
Between- 158.55 to184.51	82	66%	Moderate attitude
Above- 184.51	20	16%	High altitude
Total	124	100%	

Fig-1 Percentage of pupil teachers' attitude towards the teaching profession.

Table.3 & Fig.1.Shows that 18% of pupil teachers have a low level of attitude towards the teaching profession, 66 % of pupil teachers have a moderate level of attitude towards the

teaching profession and 16% of pupil teachers have a high level of attitude towards the teaching profession. It shows that most of the pupil teachers had an average and favorable level of attitude towards the teaching profession.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Male and Female pupil teachers' attitudes toward the teaching profession.

Table 4.1 Means, SD, and P values of male and female pupil teachers' attitudes toward the teaching profession.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	P(T<=t)two- tail	Level of Significance
Male	61	169.28	12.46	122	0.056656191	Not Significant
Female	63	173.71	13.18			

**Significant 0.05 level*

The above Table 4.1 shows that, the mean scores of male and female pupil teacher's 169.28 and 173.71 respectively with a standard deviation of 12.46 and 13.18. The female pupil teacher's mean scores are higher than the male pupil teacher's scores. The calculated P (T<=t) Two tail value (0.056656191) is greater ($p > 0.05$) than the table value at 0.05 level with Df = 122. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. "There is no significant difference between mean scores of male and female pupil teacher's attitude towards the teaching profession". Guneyli & Aslan (2009) and Sharma & Dhaiya (2012) revealed that male prospective teachers have less positive attitudes when compared to female prospective teachers.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of the Arts stream and Science stream pupil teacher's attitudes towards the teaching profession.

Table 4.2 Mean, SD, and P value of Arts and Science stream pupil teachers' attitude towards the teaching profession

Streams	N	Mean	SD	Df	P(T<=t)two- tail	Level of Significance
Arts	60	171.83	13.33	122	0.803572	Not Significant
Science	64	177.70	12.73			

** Significant 0.05 level*

Table 4.2 shows that the mean scores for Arts stream and Science stream pupil teachers are 171.83 and 177.70 respectively with a standard deviation of 13.33 and 12.73. The mean scores of science pupil teachers are higher than the mean scores of Arts pupil teacher's scores.

The calculated P (T<=t) two-tail value (0.803572) is greater ($p > 0.05$) than the table value at 0.05 level with $df = 122$. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. “There is no significant difference between mean scores of Arts and Science pupil teacher’s attitude towards teaching profession” Sharma & Dhaiya (2012) reported that Arts and Science B.Ed. Students have no significant difference in attitudes towards the profession. But contrary to this study Pehlivan (2010) revealed a significant difference between the attitude of science and social science prospective teachers.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between mean scores of Urban and Rural locality pupil teacher's attitudes towards the teaching profession

Table 4.3 Mean, SD, and P values of Urban and Rural locality pupil teachers' attitudes towards the teaching profession.

Locality	N	Mean	SD	Df	P(T<=t) two- tail	Level of Significance
Urban	40	173.20	11.62	122	0.325232	Not Significant
Rural	84	170.74	13.56			

* Significant 0.05 level.

Table 4.3 shows that the mean scores for Urban and Rural locality pupil teachers are 173.20 and 170.74 respectively with a standard deviation of 11.62 and 13.56. The mean scores of urban area pupil teachers are higher than the mean scores of rural area pupil teacher’s scores. The calculated P (T<=t) two-tail value (0.325232) is greater ($p > 0.05$) than the table value at 0.05 level with $df = 122$. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. “There is no significant difference between mean scores of urban and rural locality pupil teacher’s attitude towards teaching profession”.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Government and Self-finance pupil teachers' attitudes toward the teaching profession.

Table 4.4 Mean, SD, and P values of Government and Self-finance pupil teachers' attitudes toward the teaching profession.

Institute	N	Mean	SD	Df	P(T<=t)two-tail	Level of Significance
Government	75	168.48	12.33	122	0.000988647	Significant
Self-finance	49	176.20	12.65			

*Significant 0.05 level

Table 4.4 shows that, the mean scores of Government and Self-finance pupil teacher's 168.48 and 176.20 respectively with a standard deviation of 12.33 and 12.65. The Self-finance pupil teacher's mean scores are higher than the Government pupil teacher's scores. The calculated P (T<=t) Two tail value (0.000988647) is less ($p < 0.05$) than the table value at 0.05 level with Df = 122. Hence, the null hypothesis is not accepted. "There is a significant difference between mean scores of Government and self-finance pupil teacher's attitude towards the teaching profession". Shah and Thoker (2013) revealed that there is a significant difference between the teaching attitude of government and private secondary school teachers, and private secondary school teachers have less teaching attitude towards their teaching profession as compared to government secondary school teachers.

Conclusion and Discussion

The result of the study indicates a positive attitude of pupil teachers towards the teaching profession. Analyzing the present study results shows that pupil-teachers have favorable attitudes towards the teaching profession with 16 % of high level and 66 % with an average attitude towards the teaching profession. This favorable attitude may be because of the beliefs and values present in the pre-service B.Ed. curriculum. Yadav (1992) revealed that the teacher training program had a vital impact on the attitude of teachers toward the teaching profession. Such a favorable attitude towards the profession will ensure the quality of education in the future when these pupil teachers with such a positive attitude in future will try to serve the nation. The study also indicates that there is no significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards teaching profession gender, stream, and locality-wise. It may be because the study has been done at the very beginning of the B.Ed. course. In the future, we may expect some difference in the attitude on the above-mentioned basis. It was also found in the result of the study that there was a significant difference in the teaching attitude of the pupil-teacher studying in government and self-financed institutions.

Suggestions and Recommendation

To make the teaching profession successful, teachers must have an interest in teaching. They should not consider teaching as a means of earning a living but look at it as a noble profession. Teachers must have respect for the teaching profession. Along with this, a positive attitude towards teaching will also help to ensure the success of the teaching profession. In further research we can add components like creativity, pedagogical knowledge, technological

awareness, content competence, Values, Classroom management, Punctuality, etc. The teaching attitude of teachers at different levels of education can be studied. Attitude towards teaching can be studied in teachers of pre-service, in-service, and at different age groups. To broaden the study, its research area and sample size can be increased, so that the study can be made more reliable.

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